

Secure System for Crypto Currencies based on Virtual Accounts and Virtual Currencies

Sead Muftic^a

^a *BIX SystemTM Corporation, Washington D.C., USA*

Abstract

The paper describes the concept and details of the design of the new system that supports secure, reliable, instantaneous, and peer-to-peer transactions with crypto currencies. The most popular crypto currency is Bitcoin, but this system is also applicable to any other crypto currency. Current concepts, implementations, and operational experiences with Bitcoin and other crypto currencies have many problems. Some of them are so serious that they jeopardize future large-scale use and even survival of crypto currencies. Thus far, some solutions proposed for these problems have had unacceptable consequences, such as splitting Bitcoin into two systems, extending the block size, and speeding up validation procedures. This paper describes an innovative system with two major characteristics: (a) it solves most of the problems with current crypto currency systems, and (b) it is compatible with current systems, i.e. it does not require any of their modifications or hard fork splits. The new system is based on four innovations. First, the system introduces an additional meta-system based on the use of virtual accounts for crypto currencies. With this new approach all transactions are performed within the meta-system. Transactions with the original systems are used only occasionally for “cash-in” and “cash-out” transfers between any crypto currency and its virtual equivalent. Second, the system uses special cryptographic protocols of multi-party signatures and cryptographic enveloping to validate users’ addresses, identities, and transactions. Therefore, it does not use blocks, their chaining, miners, or any other trusted third parties. Third, the arrangements for trading crypto currencies is based on community auctions and not on centralized or distributed exchanges. Therefore, the system does not use any centralized components and performs instantaneous, truly peer-to-peer transactions. All users have full privacy and anonymity. Fourth, the system uses the method of sponsored encapsulation of accounts and user identities, which eliminates the possibility of illegal transactions such as money laundering or collecting of ransom payments.

Keywords:

Author biography

Sead Muftic Technical Expert and Adviser at The Giftz Network

January 21, 2018